

Flexible rGO-CB@Fe₃O₄/polydimethylsiloxane Composites for Electromagnetic Interference Shielding

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Abstract

Addressing the off-shoot of electromagnetic-interference, conducting polymer nanocomposites represent a novel class of materials that possess unique combination of electrical, dielectric, magnetic and mechanical properties which are useful for the suppression of electromagnetic noises. However, incorporation of various dielectric or magnetic fillers within polymer matrices without losing flexibility is a challenge. In the present work, we have investigated the effect of simultaneous incorporation of carbonaceous fillers and magnetic particles into the shielding effectiveness (SE) of single layer silicon rubber (polydimethylsiloxane). We choose carbon-black as main filler since it strengthens the rubber as-well-as modifies the electrical conductivity and dielectric permittivity of the composite. Both conductivity and SE of the composite was progressively improved with CB addition, 2-20 wt%, and attained SE ≥ 20 dB in the frequency range of 8-12 GHz, while maintaining the flexibility. Further improvement in conductivity and mechanical properties were achieved by using r-graphene oxide/CB hybrid filler. In addition, we also investigated the effect of ferromagnetic phase (Fe₃O₄) along with CB/silicon rubber composite. The hybrid structure shows excellent shielding performance originates from the combined effect of dielectric loss and magnetic loss. The complex dielectric permittivity and permeability were also determined from the measured scattering parameters. The composites possess moderate polarization and magnetization along with good conductivity due to the combined effect of multi-fillers. The hybrid structure was also characterized by various techniques such as XRD, SEM, IR, and dielectric measurements. In short, the synergetic effect of multiple fillers suggesting new pathways for designing modern light weight shielding materials.

Keywords: Composites, Silicone rubber, Shielding effectiveness

References

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